

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Optimization of Postharvest Edible Coating for Shelf Life Extension and Quality Maintenance of Fresh Cut Carrots

Navneet Kaur and Pooja Nikhanj*

Department of Microbiology, Punjab Agricultural University Ludhiana-141004, Punjab, India

*Correspondence for materials should be addressed to PN (email: poojanikhanj.217@gmail.com)

Received:

2025/01/01

Accepted:

2025/01/30

Published:

2025/02/11

Abstract

Fresh cut carrots disinfected with 100ppm sodium hypochlorite solution and coated with different coatings revealed that chitosan coating exerts higher antimicrobial efficacy and inhibits microbial growth. Characterization of chitosan coating revealed presence of functional groups responsible for antimicrobial activity and coating have low water vapour and O₂/CO₂ transmission rate with non-Newtonian flow behaviour. Standardisation of coating conditions viz. concentration and dipping time was performed using Response Surface Methodology. Results revealed that fresh cut carrots dipped in 1.0% (w/v) chitosan coating for 3 minutes exhibited lowest microbial count and maintained physicochemical properties. Validation at 5.0 kg scale showed microbial counts of coated carrot pieces were within acceptable limits (4.72 log cfu/g total plate count, 2.90 log cfu/g yeasts and moulds, and 2.95 log cfu/g total coliforms) even at 15th day, while uncoated carrots exceeded the acceptable microbial limits after 6th day of refrigeration storage. Physicochemical attributes were highly maintained and bioactive compounds including phenolics, ascorbic acid, carotenoids showed low dissipation and were highly preserved with low PPO and POD activities, thus increasing shelf life of produce. Sensory attributes showed high acceptability of chitosan coated fresh cut carrots with overall acceptability score of 7.0 on 15th day of storage.

Keywords: Chitosan; Disinfection; Edible coatings; Carrot; Shelf life; Optimization

Introduction

Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) ranked among the top 10 most economically significant vegetable crops globally (Talesh et al., 2024). Carrots is ranked among the top 10 most widely produced crops globally. In 2022, the combined production of carrots and turnips exceeded 42 million metric tons with China leading in production and Europe contributing 18.8% of the total global output. Carrots play an essential role in human nutrition and often referred as vitamin-enriched foods and immunity enhancers (Deding et al., 2020) because of their high content of antioxidants, phenolics, vitamin C and minerals. Carrots also contain variety of phytochemicals including carotenoids (such as α - and β - carotene, lycopene and lutein), phenolic compounds like caffeic acid, luteolin, myricetin and chlorogenic acid derivatives), vitamins (C, E, K, B₁ and B₄) and polyacetylenes such as falcarindiol and falcarinol. These substances are all recognized as valuable bioactive molecules. Furthermore, carrots are the richest source of β - carotene among fruits and vegetables.

In recent years, production and consumption of minimally processed vegetables have attained high popularity during and after covid-19 pandemic (Paparella et al., 2020). The reason for this positive trend is very high nutritional value, fewer additives, simple processing methods, longer shelf life along with fresh like quality attributes. Minimally processed fruits and vegetables are ready to eat unprocessed commodities that have merely been washed, peeled, sliced, chopped into completely

usable product. Recent research conducted by IFPA revealed that a weekly purchase of fresh-cut produce is made by 76.0% of consumers. However, there are growing concerns about the environmental impact of fresh cut vegetable production and potential health risks associated with exposure to these products. Minimal processing of vegetables can lead to mechanical damage and removal of protective epidermal layer which disrupts surface cells, internal tissue cells and fluids resulting in undesirable physiological changes, biochemical deterioration, texture loss, and decreased nutritional value. These factors ultimately lower the quality of fresh produce during storage (Yousuf et al., 2018). Furthermore, the creation of sub-acidic conditions, increased nutrient availability, and higher water activity create optimal conditions for the growth of spoilage and pathogenic bacteria (Deding et al., 2020).

Various postharvest management techniques have been developed for the pre-treatment of fruits and vegetables to counteract postharvest loss, enhance shelf life, and minimize microbial contamination and food borne illnesses. Among these techniques, coatings have gained significant attention in the food industry (Yousuf et al., 2018) that lowers deterioration without negatively impacting the quality of fresh cut produce and enhances the shelf life. Easier application procedure, biodegradable nature, and capable of serving as powerful obstructions towards environmental pollutants, edible coatings are a popular choice, as they dissolve on food surfaces resulting in a thin, edible film that can be deposited simply on the food or positioned within the ingredients and they intended to keep moisture, oxygen, and solutes from migrating into the food.

Hydrocolloids (proteins, polysaccharides, and alginate), lipids (fatty acids, acyl-glycerol, and waxes) are the main components used in making edible coatings, which, easily prolong the shelf life of minimally processed produce by maintaining the firmness, reducing ethylene production, preventing moisture loss, protect volatile flavours, hinder the growth of microorganisms, and enhance visual appeal of food products (Dhall, 2013). Overall, edible coatings improve nutritional quality while protecting food products from physicochemical, biochemical, and microbial degradation, such as enzymatic browning reactions, moisture loss, lipid oxidation, and microbial spoilage. Hence, the current research aims to investigate and optimize coating parameters, including concentration and dipping time with the overarching goal of advancing technology for fresh-cut carrot production.

Material and methods

Materials

Freshly harvested carrots were procured from vegetable farm of Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. Selected carrots were mature, displayed good quality, and were devoid of any visible defects with consistent size, colour, and weight.

Methods

Pre-disinfection of fresh cut carrots

Carrots were washed, peeled; calyx was removed, cut into equivalent sized juliennes with sterilized knife. Fresh cut carrots were examined for their physical and biochemical properties. Afterwards, carrots were disinfected in 100ppm concentration sodium hypochlorite solution for 8 minutes at $10 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (Nikhanj and Kaur, 2022).

Evaluation of coatings

Starch, alginate, pectin, carboxymethyl cellulose, chitosan, and carrageenan coatings were prepared following established protocols provided by various researchers (Lin et al., 2017; Saba and Sogyar, 2016; Qi et al., 2011; Tapia et al., 2008; Oms- oliu et al., 2008; Garcia et al., 2006). Each treatment involved using 250 grams of pre-disinfected fresh-cut carrots. Fresh-cut carrots were immersed in different coating solutions (ranging from 1.0% to 5.0% w/v) for durations spanning from 3 to 15 minutes (Benitez et al., 2013). Subsequently, they were air dried before being packaged in airtight Polyethyleneterephthalate (PET) containers followed by refrigeration storage at $5-7^\circ\text{C}$. Uncoated fresh-cut carrots were taken as control samples. The coating that exhibited the most significant microbial inhibition while maintaining favourable physicochemical characteristics was chosen for further standardization studies.

Characterization of selected coating

Selected coating was characterized for its thickness (using micrometer), water vapor permeability, O_2 & CO_2 permeability measured by modified ASTM (2012) Standard Test Method), FTIR analysis (Agilent spectrophotometer) and rheological behavior using rheometer (Anton Paar, MCR 92).

Standardization of coating conditions

Standardization of coating conditions was conducted using Central Composite Rotatable Design (CCRD) following Response Surface Methodology (RSM). The study focused on two independent variables: concentration and dipping time. A total of 13 experimental runs, each with varying combinations were performed using 250 grams of fresh-cut carrots for each run. After completing these 13 experimental runs, the responses were analyzed in terms of physicochemical properties and microbial counts on the fresh-cut carrots until the samples showed signs of deterioration.

Validation and shelf-life study

Standardization conditions were validated at 5.0 kg scale to check the production desirability with the optimized results. Freshly cut carrots that have been peeled, pre-disinfected, and coated under standardized conditions with selected coating, were placed in PTE containers and stored at 5-7°C for 15 days with physicochemical and microbial parameters analysis at regular intervals of 3 days.

Analytical methods

Weight loss (%) is calculated by taking difference between fresh and final weight which was later on divided by its fresh weight. A penetrometer (Model-FT 327, Canada) with a 6.0 ±0.05 mm probe is used to determine the sample firmness. The modulus of elasticity (E) was calculated using a texture analyzer (Stable Micro Systems, UK) following by quasi-static compression test. Each carrot slice was measured in triplicate around its center equator and E calculated according to ASAE as

$$E = 0.531 \times F \times (1 - \mu) \times (2R + d) \quad (6)$$

Where μ = Poisson's ratio is 0.49, d is diameter 12.7 mm and R is radius of the cucumber slice.

CO₂ release was estimated with a SDS gas analyzer using punching needle system that measures the respiration rate within the container indicating the maturity index of the cucumber slices. Bench top pH meter (Mettler Toledo pH meter, US) was used to determine the pH of sample, while acidity of the samples was measured by crushing the sample and then titration of sample with 0.1M of NaOH using phenolphthalein as the indicator. Total soluble solids were determined by using Erma Hand refractometer. Total sugars and ascorbic acid content was calculated using method described by Dubois et al., 1956 and Singh et al., 2023. Total phenols were quantified following Malik and Singh (1991) method. Total carotenoids were quantified using colorimetric method based on Jagannath et al. (2006). Colour characteristics of sample in terms of L*, a* and b* values were measured by using a spectrophotometer CM-3600d (Minolta Co., Tokyo, Japan). Obtained values were further used to calculate the whiteness index (WI).

$$WI = 100 \frac{C_{ab}^* = \sqrt{a^{*2} + b^{*2}}}{\sqrt{(100 - L^*)^2 + a^{*2} + b^{*2}}}$$

Methodology outlined by Galeazzi et al., (1981) was followed to measure the Polyphenol oxidase (PPO) Peroxidase (POD), enzymatic activity respectively. Microbial count such as total plate count (TPC), yeasts and moulds (Y&M), total coliforms (TC) in both pre-treated and post-treated samples was determined through a serial dilution technique following FSSAI manual, 2016 method.

Sensory analysis

A semi-trained panel of 10 judges evaluated the sensory attribute on the basis of appearance, colour, texture, odour, off-odour, flavour, off-flavour and overall acceptability on a 9 point hedonic scale.

Rheological behaviour of the coating

Rheology of selected coating was determined by rheometer (Anton Paar, MCR 92) using plate geometry (25 mm diameter) with 1 mm gap. Viscosity was measured by applying steady shear test in the range of 0-100 s⁻¹ and behaviour of storage and loss modulus values was determined by applying frequency oscillatory sweep test in the strain range of 0.01-100% at 1Hz frequency at 25°C.

Fourier transforms infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

The FTIR spectra of coating to assess the functional groups was measured at wavelengths ranging between 500-4,000 cm⁻¹ using FTIR spectrophotometer (Aligent Cary 630 FTIR)

Statistical analysis

Results were presented as sum of three independent observations, \pm standard deviation. RSM, ANOVA was used to examine the data and T-test was used to evaluate means at ($P < 0.05$) using Design expert 11 software and SPSS Statistical Software version 18.0.

Results and discussion

Disinfection and screening of coatings

Pre-disinfection of fresh cut carrots in 100 ppm sodium hypochlorite solution resulted in significant reduction of 0.94 log cfu/g of Total Plate Count (TPC), 0.54 log cfu/g of Yeasts & Mold Count (Y & M) and 0.73 log cfu/g of Total Coliforms Count, while physicochemical parameters varied non-significantly after the disinfection pre-treatment. Pre-disinfected fresh cut carrots were coated with six different coatings (1.0-5.0% w/v) to evaluate their microbicidal efficacy. After evaluating the data, it was found that fresh cut carrots coated with chitosan showed maximum microbial inhibition during storage period and had 3.85 log cfu/g TPC, 2.47 log cfu/g Y&M count and 2.69 log cfu/g total coliforms count at 9th day of storage period. Chitosan coating showed the significantly higher microbial inhibition efficiency along with maintenance of all physicochemical and nutritive properties as compared to other coatings (Fig. 1). Sharma et al. (2019) observed retardation of *Alternaria alternata* and other fungal growth on chitosan coated tomatoes as compared to uncoated samples. Olawuyi et al. (2019) also reported reduction in microflora load on acidified sodium hypochlorite solution treated followed by chitosan coated fresh cut vegetables. Therefore, chitosan coating was selected for further optimization studies based upon inhibiting the microbial growth and maintenance of physicochemical characteristics.

Fig. 1. Microbial count over differently coated fresh cut carrot at 0 and 9th day of storage (TPC- Total plate count; Y& M- Yeast and moulds count)

Characterization of chitosan coating

Chitosan coating had adequate adhesive properties and uniform distribution on the treated fresh cut carrot samples. Masses mean of dried coatings on a treated surface was $2.6 \pm 0.32 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$, corresponding to a film thickness of about $24.0 \pm 3.0 \mu\text{m}$. Low water vapor ($3.21 \pm 0.67 \text{ mg/mL cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) and low O_2/CO_2 transmission values 1.23 ± 0.29 & 1.95 ± 0.20 of the chitosan coating with permeability rate of $17.08 \pm 1.74 \text{ mg/mL } \mu\text{m kPa}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ revealed that it can serve as efficient barrier between fresh cut carrot and the environmental conditions. Chitosan coating showed a shear thinning, pseudo plastic, non – Newtonian behaviour as their viscosity value decreased with increase in shear rate may be due to breakage of microstructures gradually in the colloidal system and interactions between biopolymer–water were lower than biopolymer–biopolymer interactions. Similar behaviour of chitosan coating was observed by Sobral et al., (2022) and reported the consequence of chitosan coating of different concentrations and non-Newtonian behaviour overall. FTIR analysis of the chitosan coating revealed two characteristic peaks at 1636 and 3263 cm^{-1} equivalent to the mutual peaks of the amide I group and OH - NH^2 groups - stretching vibrations, respectively in coating.

Standardization of coating conditions

Pre-disinfected fresh cut carrots were dipped in the chitosan coating of different concentrations levels for different time period according to RSM plan (Table 1). Responses were taken in terms of evaluating microbial parameters like Y&M, TPC and TC in addition to physicochemical parameters viz. pH, firmness, TSS, total sugars. Results presented in table 1 revealed that 3.0 minutes dipping of fresh cut carrots in 1.0% (w/v) chitosan coating exhibits lowest microbial count in terms of TPC, Y&M and Total coliforms on 9th day of storage while maintaining all physicochemical properties of the produce.

All the model values for the response parameters were significant with non-significant lack of fit. The values for adjusted R² and predicted R² were in reasonable agreement and p-values <0.05 indicating good fitness of the model with high significance (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of concentration and dipping time on physicochemical and microbial parameters of fresh cut carrot

Run	% coating Concentration (w/v)	Dipping time (minutes)	pH	TSS (°Brix)	Firmness (lb/inch)	Total sugars (g/100g)	TPC (log cfu/g)	Y&M (log cfu/g)	Total Coliforms (log cfu/g)
1	3	9	6.7	7.4	18.5	7.5	4.0	2.6	2.8
2	5.8	9	6.7	7.2	21.2	6.0	3.9	1.6	2.5
3	5	15	6.8	7.3	16.0	6.0	4.0	2.0	2.6
4	3	9	6.7	7.5	17.5	7.8	3.9	2.7	2.8
5	1	15	6.8	7.7	16.0	6.1	3.9	2.7	2.6
6	3	0.5	6.6	7.8	22.0	6.9	4.1	2.0	2.5
7	5	3	6.7	7.1	23.0	5.7	4.0	1.7	2.7
8	1	3	6.6	8.1	22.0	7.0	3.7	1.5	2.1
9	3	9	6.8	7.5	18.0	7.5	4.2	2.7	2.9
10	0.17	9	6.7	7.0	18.0	7.4	3.8	2.5	2.2
11	3	17.4	6.8	7.6	14.3	5.8	4.0	2.5	2.7
12	3	9	6.7	7.4	18.2	8.0	3.9	2.6	2.8
13	3	9	6.7	7.5	19.1	7.9	4.0	2.7	2.7
Model value			17.89	37.12	29.26	24.21	31.9	27.57	1102.61
Predicted R² Values			0.738	0.8077	0.7693	0.7152	0.8043	0.7203	0.9925
Adjusted R² Values			0.875	0.9377	0.9217	0.9063	0.9264	0.9172	0.9978
P Value			0.000	0.0001	0.0001	0.0003	0.0001	0.0002	<0.0001

TSS: Total Soluble Solids; TPC: Total Plate Count; Y&M: Yeast and Mold count; cfu: Colony forming units

3D images shown in Fig. 2 (a, b and c) represent the interaction graphs between significant factors responsible for microbial growth. Coating concentration and dipping time are the most influential parameters to be studied for a coating process. Antimicrobial effect of the coating is depending upon two above said factors that describes the effectiveness of the coating. The interaction between the two holds the efficacy of the coating process. Fig. 2 explained the concentration and dipping time effect upon the microbial count over fresh cut carrots. With the increase in the concentration of the coating up to 3% (w/v) and dipping time upto 6 minutes, the microbial inhibition in terms of TPC, Y&M and total coliforms was reduced. However, the reduction is non-significant at both lower concentration and dipping time. Hence, minimum concentration and dipping time was optimized for the coating process.

Validation of the results was performed at 5.0 kg fresh cut carrots scale (500 g capacity containers having 300 g fresh cut carrots). Optimized carrots showed firmness of 25.5 lb, with 6.8 g/100g of total sugars, 8.0°B of TSS, pH of 6.5, with total plate count (TPC), Y&M count and total coliforms count of 3.9, 1.8, and 2.0 log cfu/g, respectively, which were in agreement with RSM plan with 93% desirability rate.

Shelf-life studies

1.0% (w/v) chitosan coated fresh cut carrots under standardized conditions were stored under refrigeration to determine its shelf life. Different physicochemical parameters and bioactive compounds along with enzymatic activities were observed during the storage period (Table 2 and 3). Physicochemical parameters showed less significant difference over the storage period of 15 days in terms of pH (5.1-5.2), TSS (8.0-8.5°B), firmness 18.75-18.65 (lb) and colour (whitening index) while uncoated samples had significant difference in all physicochemical parameters. During storage, ageing and ripening of fresh cut vegetables occurs, reduces organic acids that provides

most of the hydrogen ions causing an increase in pH. Control samples had higher TSS value in comparison to coated sample sowing to hydrolysis of cell wall occurs and starch is converted into soluble sugars during the storage period. Firmness tended to decrease during 9 days of storage period while chitosan coated samples' firmness decreases non significantly maintaining the tenderness of the fresh cut carrot. Firmness loss can be attributed by moisture loss, ripening, tissue senescence caused by microbes and tissue-degrading enzymes and breakdown of cell wall. The colour WI index of uncoated fresh cut carrots increased gradually throughout storage period as compared to coated samples. The whitening of peeled carrots in uncoated samples was associated with dehydration of external damaged cells and structural alteration occurred during processing and storage of carrot slice. Similar results were found by Chen et al., (2023) during their studies on white blush in carrots.

Fig. 2. Effect of coating concentration and dipping time on (2a) TPC (2b) Y&M and (2c) total coliforms

Coatings having high equilibrium moisture content (0.63g water/g film) w.r.t. high water activity of carrot slices helps to keep plant tissue surface moist and minimizes surface discoloration in coated samples. In general, control carrots have low WI, while chitosan coating increase their WI. This decline may be attributed to factors such as surface desiccation, damage to carotenoids, and a reduction in nutritional content, all of which contribute to a decrease in the product shelf life. Weight loss and RI were found to be significantly decreased in both uncoated and coated fresh cut carrots. Though, these reductions in chitosan coated carrots are very less in comparison to the uncoated samples. Sugar and acid profiling of coated fresh cut carrots revealed that sugar content increased gradually as compared to uncoated samples, while titratable acidity decreased non-

significantly in both control and coated samples. Bioactive compounds in terms of total phenolics, ascorbic acid and total carotenoids analysis revealed that loss of the bioactive compounds was significantly less in the coated samples because they form a barrier between outer surface of vegetable and its surroundings which reduces oxygen diffusion and decelerate respiration rate during shelf life. Similarly, enzymatic activity (PPO and POD) increased significantly lower in coated samples than the uncoated samples. Phenols and flavonoids are secondary metabolites present in vegetables which protects tissues of human body against oxidative attacks (Alegria et al., 2012).

Table 2. Physicochemical parameters and bioactive compounds analysis of chitosan coated fresh cut carrots during storage

Parameters	Sample	Storage time (days)					
		0	3	6	9	12	15
pH	Coated	5.10 ± 0.15 ^a	5.10 ± 0.16 ^a	5.10 ± 0.13 ^a	5.10 ± 0.12 ^a	5.20 ± 0.11 ^a	5.20 ± 0.06 ^b
	Uncoated	5.20 ± 0.15 ^a	5.20 ± 0.01 ^a	5.30 ± 0.01 ^b	ND	ND	ND
TSS (°Brix)	Coated	8.00 ± 0.12 ^c	8.20 ± 0.11 ^b	8.20 ± 0.12 ^b	8.3 ± 0.11 ^b	8.3 ± 0.11 ^b	8.5 ± 0.11 ^a
	Uncoated	8.00 ± 0.12 ^c	8.30 ± 0.10 ^b	8.50 ± 0.11 ^a	ND	ND	ND
Firmness (lb/inch)	Coated	18.75 ± 0.12 ^a	18.75 ± 0.11 ^a	18.72 ± 0.10 ^b	18.70 ± 0.12 ^c	18.67 ± 0.12 ^d	18.65 ± 0.11 ^e
	Uncoated	18.70 ± 0.11 ^a	16.23 ± 0.12 ^b	15.05 ± 0.13 ^c	ND	ND	ND
Ripening index	Coated	50.00 ± 0.03 ^e	50.62 ± 0.05 ^d	54.06 ± 0.02 ^c	54.13 ± 0.09 ^c	58.07 ± 0.04 ^b	58.14 ± 0.06 ^a
	Uncoated	50.00 ± 0.01 ^c	55.19 ± 0.04 ^b	59.30 ± 0.03 ^a	ND	NA	NA
Weight loss (%)	Coated	NA	0.8 ± 0.02 ^d	1.2 ± 0.01 ^c	1.3 ± 0.03 ^c	2.4 ± 0.01 ^b	3.1 ± 0.04 ^a
	Uncoated	NA	2.1 ± 0.3 ^b	4.1 ± 0.2 ^a	NA	NA	NA
Colour (WI)	Coated	21.7 ± 0.02 ^a	21.5 ± 0.05 ^b	21.0 ± 0.01 ^b	21.0 ± 0.02 ^b	21.0 ± 0.03 ^b	20.5 ± 0.02 ^c
	Uncoated	22.8 ± 0.04 ^a	20.1 ± 0.03 ^b	18.0 ± 0.06 ^c	NA	NA	NA
Total sugars (g/100g)	Coated	Coated	6.66 ± 0.02 ^a	6.68 ± 0.04 ^a	6.69 ± 0.02 ^a	6.72 ± 0.02 ^b	6.72 ± 0.04 ^b
	Uncoated	Uncoated	6.52 ± 0.03 ^c	6.82 ± 0.07 ^b	7.19 ± 0.04 ^a	ND	ND
Titratable acidity (%)	Coated	Coated	0.16 ± 0.01 ^a	0.17 ± 0.01 ^a	0.15 ± 0.02 ^a	0.15 ± 0.02 ^a	0.15 ± 0.01 ^a
	Uncoated	Uncoated	0.15 ± 0.01 ^b	0.16 ± 0.01 ^b	0.18 ± 0.02 ^a	ND	ND
Total phenols (mg/100g)	Coated	Coated	46.0 ± 1.2 ^a	44.3 ± 1.0 ^b	41.4 ± 2.2 ^c	40.4 ± 2.1 ^c	38.9 ± 1.5 ^c
	Uncoated	Uncoated	44.7 ± 1.6 ^a	35.3 ± 1.5 ^b	28.9 ± 2.1 ^c	ND	ND
Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)	Coated	Coated	20.2 ± 0.1 ^a	20.2 ± 0.2 ^a	19.2 ± 0.2 ^b	19.1 ± 0.1 ^b	17.6 ± 0.2 ^c
	Uncoated	Uncoated	20.0 ± 0.2 ^a	17.9 ± 0.3 ^b	14.2 ± 0.1 ^c	ND	ND
Total carotenoids (mg/100g)	Coated	Coated	37.8 ± 0.2 ^a	36.6 ± 0.4 ^b	36.0 ± 0.1 ^c	35.7 ± 0.2 ^d	30.9 ± 0.3 ^e
	Uncoated	Uncoated	37.1 ± 0.3 ^a	28.0 ± 0.2 ^b	22.8 ± 0.4 ^c	ND	ND
PPO activity (U/g)	Coated	Coated	135 ± 1.38 ^f	141 ± 1.58 ^e	169 ± 2.03 ^d	178 ± 1.75 ^c	184 ± 1.45 ^b
	Uncoated	Uncoated	137 ± 1.29 ^c	178 ± 2.91 ^b	193 ± 1.08 ^a	ND	ND
POD activity (U/g)	Coated	Coated	0.50 ± 0.02 ^f	1.34 ± 0.10 ^e	2.76 ± 0.04 ^d	4.22 ± 0.21 ^c	5.12 ± 0.07 ^b
	Uncoated	Uncoated	0.70 ± 0.05 ^c	4.74 ± 0.90 ^b	6.76 ± 0.14 ^a	ND	ND

Data represents mean (n=3) ± SD; Values having different superscripts are significantly (p<0.05) different from each other row wise; ND: Not determined; The uncoated sample got deteriorated after 6 days of storage, due to which no further studies were performed on it.

The microbial count in chitosan-coated fresh-cut carrots remained within acceptable limits even after 15 days of storage, with a recorded count of 4.72 log cfu/g for TPC, 2.90 log cfu/g for Y&M, and 2.95 log cfu/g for total coliforms. In contrast, the uncoated samples exceeded the acceptable microbial limits by the 6th day of storage, with counts of 5.24 log cfu/g for TPC, 3.39 log cfu/g for Y&M, and 3.44 log cfu/g for total coliforms. The bactericidal properties of chitosan responsible for maintain microbial count occurs due to interaction between positively charged amino groups of chitosan and negatively charged membranes of microbial cell that causes the leakage of intracellular components from the microbes. Sensory evaluation of both coated and uncoated fresh-cut carrots using a panel of ten semi-trained tasters was performed. Colour and appearance of coated samples were acceptable whereas uncoated carrot samples were not acceptable after 12 days of storage. Chitosan coating was able to control white colour discoloration up to 15 days of storage. Uncoated samples developed off-odour during storage whereas chitosan coated samples appeared to be fresh till 15 days of storage. It was observed that uncoated samples developed off-flavour which was not acceptable after 9 days. The sensory score for both coated and uncoated samples was 8.5 points for over-all acceptability on the hedonic scale at day 0, indicating that the treatment did not significantly impact the sensory attributes of the samples. By the 15th day of storage, coated fresh-cut carrots received a satisfactory sensory score of 7 points, which is considered good from the consumer's perspective. Shelf-life studies demonstrated that chitosan-coated fresh-cut carrots, when pre-treated, can be safely consumed up to the 15th day of refrigerated storage.

Conclusion

Fresh cut carrots coated with 1.0% (w/v) chitosan prolonged the shelf life of carrots from 6 days to 15 days at a temperature of 5-7°C during storage. Chitosan based coating proved to be effective in preventing microbiological spoilage without compromising with their physicochemical properties and keeping its sensory qualities and nutritional value intact. They also prevented surface whitening, improved colour retention and maintained product texture throughout storage period. Moreover, Chitosan is derived from the industrial processing of shell waste from seafood industry that symbolizes a value-added by-product of processing. So, utilizing waste products from the food industry to create active coatings can enhance sustainability in the food sector.

References

- Alegria C, Pinheiro J, Duthoit M, et al. (2012) Fresh-cut carrot (cv. Nantes) quality as affected by abiotic stress (heat shock and UV-C irradiation) pre-treatments. *LWT-Food Sci Technol* 48(2):197-203. DOI: 10.1016/j.lwt.2012.03.013.
- Benítez S, Achaerandio I, Sepulcre F, et al. (2013) Aloe vera based edible coatings improve the quality of minimally processed 'Hayward' kiwifruit. *Postharvest Biol Technol* 81: 29-36. DOI:10.1016/j.postharvbio.2013.02.009.
- Chen W, Wu H, Zou Y, et al. (2023) Effects of Different Treatments on White-blush of Fresh-cut Carrots During Storage. In *BIOWeb of Conferences* (Vol. 59, p. 01020). EDP Sciences. DOI: 10.1051/bioconf/20235901020.
- Deding U, Baatrup G, Christensen LP, et al. (2020) Carrot intake and risk of colorectal cancer: A prospective cohort study of 57,053 Danes. *Nutr* 12(2):332. DOI: 10.3390/nu12020332.
- Dhall RK (2013) Advances in edible coatings for fresh fruits and vegetables: a review. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr* 53(5):435-450. DOI: 10.1080/10408398.2010.541568.
- Do Amaral Sobral PJ, Gebremariam G, Drudi F, et al. (2022) Rheological and viscoelastic properties of chitosan solutions prepared with different chitosan or acetic acid concentrations. *Food* 11(17): 2692.
- Dubois M, Gilles KA, Hamilton JK, et al. (1956) *Anal Chem* 28:350-356.
- Galeazzi MAM and Sgarbieri VC (1981) Substrate specificity and inhibition of polyphenoloxidase (PPO) from a dwarf variety of banana (Muss CavendishiiL.). *J Food Sci* 46(5):1404-1406. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2621.1981.tb04184.x.
- Garcia MA, Pinotti A and Zarithky NE (2006) Physicochemical, water vapour barrier and mechanical properties of corn starch and chitosan composite films. *Starch* 58(9): 453-463. DOI: 10.1002/star.200500484.
- Jagannath JH, Nanjappa C, Gupta DD, et al. (2006) Studies on the stability of an edible film and its use for the preservation of carrot (*Daucus carota*). *IJFST* 41(5):498-506. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2621.2005.01038.x.
- Lin MG, Lasekan O, Saari N, et al. (2017) The effect of the application of edible coatings on or before ultraviolet treatment on postharvested longan fruits. *J Food Qual* 54: 542-563. DOI: 10.1155/2017/5454263.
- Malik CP and Singh M (1980) *Plant enzymology and histo-enzymology*. Kalyani publishers, New Delhi.
- Nikhanj P and Kaur G (2022) Optimization of disinfection treatment for shelf life extension of fresh cut salad vegetables. *J Food Eng Technol* 11(1): 1-12. DOI: 0.32732/jfet.2022.11.1.1
- Olawuyi IF, Park JJ, Lee JJ, et al. (2019) Combined effect of chitosan coating and modified atmosphere packaging on fresh-cut cucumber. *Food Sci Nutr* 7(3):1043-1052. DOI: 10.1002/fsn3.937.
- Oms-Oliu G, Soliva-Fortuny R and Martín-Belloso O (2008) Using polysaccharide-based edible coatings to enhance quality and antioxidant properties of fresh-cut melon. *LWT-Food Sci Technol* 41(10):1862-1870. DOI: 10.1016/j.lwt.2008.01.007.
- Paparella A, Purgatorio C, Chaves-López C, et al. (2022) The multifaceted relationship between the COVID-19 pandemic and the food system. *Foods* 11(18): 2816.
- Qi H, Hu W, Jiang A, et al. (2011) Extending shelf-life of fresh-cut 'Fuji' apples with chitosan-coatings. *IFSET* 12(1):62-66.

Saba MK and Sogvar OB (2016) Combination of carboxymethyl cellulose-based coatings with calcium and ascorbic acid impacts in browning and quality of fresh-cut apples. *LWT-Food Sci Technol* 66:165-171. DOI: 10.1016/j.lwt.2015.10.022.

Sharma P, Shehin VP, Kaur N, et al. (2019) Application of edible coatings on fresh and minimally processed vegetables: a review. *Int J Veg Sci* 25(3): 295-314. DOI: 10.1080/19315260.2018.1510863.

Singh P, Kaur G, Singh A, et al. (2023) Effect of montmorillonite and starch nanocrystals based biodegradable films loaded with lemongrass oil nanoemulsion on quality, enzymatic activity and shelf life of strawberry. *Food Chem Adv* 3:335-343. DOI: 10.1016/j.focha.2023.100343.

Talesh AA, Amiri S, Radi M, et al. (2024) Effect of nanocomposite alginate-based edible coatings containing thymol-nanoemulsion and/or thymol-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers on the microbial and physicochemical properties of carrot. *Int J Biol Macromol* 12: 91-96. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.129196.

Tapia MS, Rojas-Graü MA, Carmona A, et al. (2008) Use of alginate-and gellan-based coatings for improving barrier, texture and nutritional properties of fresh-cut papaya. *Food Hydrocoll* 22(8): 1493-1503. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodhyd.2007.10.004.

Yousuf B, Qadri OS and Srivastava AK (2018) Recent developments in shelf-life extension of fresh-cut fruits and vegetables by application of different edible coatings: A review. *LWT-Food Sci Technol* 89: 198-209. DOI: 10.1016/j.lwt.2017.10.051.

Author Contributions

NK and PN conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Visit for more details <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Citation: Kaur N and Nikhanj P (2025) Optimization of Postharvest Edible Coating for Shelf Life Extension and Quality Maintenance of Fresh Cut Carrots. *Environmental Science Archives* 4(1): 96-104.